

Terpenoids. Part. LXXV. A New Synthesis of 3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\alpha}$ -Cyclohexane acetaldehyde

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Synthesis of 3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\alpha}$ -cyclohexaneacetaldehyde has been effected through the application of modified Wittig reaction of ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate on 3,3-dimethyl cyclohexanone.

In continuation to our experiments¹⁻³, directed towards the syntheses of various terpenoids through modified Wittig reaction on appropriate aldehydes and ketones, we report in this communication a pliant synthesis of the insect sex attractant, 3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\alpha}$ -cyclohexaneacetaldehyde.

The sexpheromone was found to occur in the frass or fecal material of male California fine-spined, ips, *Ips confusus*⁴ (Le Conte). Steam distillation of the extract of fecal material of boll weevils produced a material highly attractive to females but not to males^{5,6}. The biologically active compound has been assigned the constitution(I) on the basis of spectral data which has been further confirmed through a synthesis^{7*}.

The recent concern over pollution of our environment and ecological imbalance caused by insecticides has stimulated interest in this area. Possibility of this sex attractant for providing a nontoxic method of controlling insect population encouraged us to effect a new straightforward synthesis for it (Scheme I).

The starting material, 3,3-dimethyl cyclohexanone (II) prepared from 3-methyl-2-cyclohexen-1-one by the method of Buchi *et al.*⁹ was submitted to modified Wittig reaction¹⁰ with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate in presence of sodium hydride using diethyl-glycoldimethyl ether as solvent, when 3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\alpha}$ -cyclohexane ethyl acetate was obtained in 74% yield. The unsaturated ester (III) was then reduced with lithium aluminium hydride

* Another synthesis of the title compound has recently been reported in literature⁸.

in dry benzene¹¹ to obtain in 69% yield the boll weevil sex attractant alcohol(IV) which was oxidised with manganese dioxide¹² to complete the synthesis of 3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\alpha}$ -cyclohexaneacetaldehyde (I). Though the tlc of the compound showed two spots possibly due to the presence of mixture of *cis* and *trans* isomers, its identity was established through its IR spectrum by comparison with the one reported in the literature⁷.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film. The microanalyses were done by Mr. L. K. Khullar.

3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\alpha}$ -cyclohexaneethylacetate (III): Sodium hydride (3.9 g) was placed in 1,2-diethylglycoldimethyl ether (100 ml.). Ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate (19.2 g.) was added dropwise below 20° with stirring and the solution was stirred further until the gas evolution had ceased. To the resulting solution was then added the ketone (II, 6.5 g.) slowly below 25°. After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 3 hr. and then refluxed for 30 min. at 60°. The product was extracted with ether after decomposing with a large excess of water, dried (anh. Na₂SO₄) and evaporated. Distillation of the residue under reduced pressure provided α,β -unsaturated ester (III, 7.5 g.) in 74% yield, b.p. 125°/10 mm, η^{29}_D 1.4510 (Found : C, 72.60; H, 11.00. C₁₂H₂₂O₂ requires C, 72.68; H, 11.18%). ν_{max} 1740, 1660, 1470, 1380, 1260, 1160, 1035, 970, 870 and 840 cm⁻¹.

3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\beta}$ -cyclohexaneethanol (IV): To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1.5 g.) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added with stirring the α,β -unsaturated ester (III, 5 g.) in benzene (10 ml) and the mixture heated (60°–70°) for about 15 hr. The contents were cooled and decomposed with 20% solution of sodium potassium tartrate. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether. The combined ether-benzene extract was dried over sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvents, the product was distilled under reduced pressure to yield 3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\beta}$ -cyclohexaneethanol (IV, 2.7 g.) in 69% yield, b.p. 105°/10 mm., η^{29}_D 1.4750 (Found : C, 77.76; H, 11.55. C₁₀H₁₈O requires C, 77.86; H, 11.76%). ν_{max} 3600, 1680, 1470, 1380 and 1040 cm⁻¹.

3,3-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1,\alpha}$ -cyclohexaneacetaldehyde (I): The alcohol (IV, 1 g.) was added to a suspension of active manganese dioxide (10 g) in 150 ml of *n*-hexane. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously for 7 hr. and the solid separated from the mixture by filtration and the residue washed with *n*-hexane. The combined solvent was concentrated under nitrogen atmosphere and the residue chromatographed over neutral alumina using pet. ether (40°–60°). Distillation under vacuum afforded the α,β -unsaturated aldehyde (I, 0.5 g.) in 50% yield, b.p. 95°/10 mm, η^{29}_D 1.4680 (Found : C, 78.75; H, 10.45. C₁₀H₁₆O requires C, 78.89; H, 10.59%). ν_{max} 1690, 1640, 1460, 1370, 1170, 1120, 1040, 850 and 725 cm⁻¹.

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